

New information on the green tree crab spider *Oxytate argenteooculata* (Simon, 1886) from South Africa (Araneae: Thomisidae)

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ABSTRACT: The genus *Oxytate* L. Koch, 1878 is represented by 30 species and six are known from the Afrotropical Region. One of the species, *Oxytate argenteooculata* (Simon, 1886), is found throughout the region. New Information on their morphology, behaviour, distribution and conservation status in South Africa is here provided.

Key words: agroecosystems, biodiversity, egg sac, avocado orchard, South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA)

INTRODUCTION

The genus *Oxytate* L. Koch, 1878 is known from 30 species, of which six have been recorded from the Afrotropical Region. Information on these species described between 1886 and 1964 is limited and outdated (World Spider Catalog, 2022).

As part of the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA), large numbers of arachnid specimens were sampled (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015) and one of them was identified as *Oxytate argenteooculata* (Simon, 1886).

This African endemic species was described by Simon (1886) as *Dieta argenteooculata* from Zanzibar, but Song *et al.* (1982) considered *Oxytate* a senior synonym of *Dieta* Simon, 1880 and the species was transferred to *Oxytate*. It has since then been sampled from several countries in the Afrotropical Region. Little is still known about them in South Africa and the aim of this paper is to provide information on their morphology based on live specimens, behaviour, distribution, and conservation status.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Voucher specimens of *O. argenteooculata* sampled during SANSA surveys are deposited in the National Collection of Arachnida (NCA) at the Agricultural Research Council, Pretoria. Numerous photographs were submitted by the public for identification as part of the SANSA Virtual Museum database (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2012).

TAXONOMY

Oxytate argenteooculata (Simon, 1886)

Dieta argenteooculata Simon, 1886: 179 (f); Simon, 1895: 981(f); Lessert, 1919: 99 (m); Lessert, 1928: 306 (f); Lessert, 1943: 311 (m).

Dieta argenteooculata Jézéquel, 1964: 1107 (f).

Oxytate argenteooculata Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2014: 243; Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2022: part 2: 1819 (m & f).

Diagnostic characteristics: Size: TL female and male 5–8 mm. Live members are recognised by their green bodies decorated with red spots, but the green colour fades in alcohol. The green of the body varies from translucent pale green (Figs 1–2) to darker green (Fig. 3), while the colour of the legs in males varies from green to pale brown (Figs 12–13). Carapace: circular, flattened, with thin reddish brown marginal band; the colour of the marginal band varies from reddish brown (Fig. 14) to brown (Fig. 23); band sometimes absent in juveniles; four small reddish spots are present on both sides of fovea (Figs 1–3), sometimes only two (Fig. 23); chelicerae wide; eyes in two

Figs 1–3. *Oxytate argenteooculata*: 1. Female anterior view of eyes. 2. Female on leaf, dorsal view. 3. Female dorsal view. Photos: 1–2. Bruce Blake. 3. Peter Webb.

Figs 4–11. *Oxytate argenteooculata*: 4. Line drawing, male palp. 5. Male palp, retrotibial apophysis. 6–7. Male palp dorsal view and lateral view. 8. Epigyne. 9. Line drawing, epigyne. 10. Line drawing, eye pattern. 11. Line drawing, carapace lateral view. Photos: 4. Lessert (1919). 5. Lessert (1943). 6–8. A. Dippenaar-Schoeman. 9. Jézéquel (1964). 10–11. Simon (1895).

recurved rows (Figs 1 & 10), anterior row shorter than posterior row; eyes on small, flat, white tubercles; median eyes smaller than lateral eyes; anterior lateral eyes the largest (Figs 1 & 23); median ocular area longer than wide.

Abdomen green, elongated with spotted appearance; posterior third with transverse paired rows of 6–8 thick setae (Fig. 3). Legs spotted; distal segments paler; two anterior legs longer than the posterior legs; tibiae and metatarsi with biseriate long macrosetae (Fig. 18); tarsal claws long and narrow with 8 to 13 teeth; femora of all the legs with erect strong setae anterior laterally (Figs 1–2). Male palp with long retrolateral apophysis with tip curved (Figs 4–7); atrium of epigyne heart shaped (Figs 8–9).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION

Zanzibar; Tanzania (Kibonoto Kilimandjaro) (Lessert, 1919); Democratic Republic of the Congo (Faradje, Medje, Poko) (Lessert, 1928); Zambia (iNaturalist); Eswatini; South Africa (NCA); Mozambique.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA

Eastern Cape: Jeffreys Bay (-34.06, 24.91); Kei River Mouth (-32.68, 28.37); Middelburg (-31.49, 24.99); Thyspunt, (-34.206, 24.708); Addo Elephant National Park (-33.32, 25.72). **Free State:** Bloemfontein (-29.05, 26.2). **Gauteng:** Cullinan Premier Game Farm (-25.67, 28.48); Irene (-25.89, 28.23); Ezemvelo Nature Reserve (-25.8, 28.77). **KwaZulu-Natal:** iSimangaliso Wetland Park; uMkuzi Game Reserve (-27.63, 32.25); Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.87, 32.24); Pietermaritzburg (-29.61, 30.38). **Limpopo:** Luvhondo Nature Reserve (-23.03, 29.45); Little Leigh (Western Soutpansberg) (-22.95, 29.87); Nylsvley Nature Reserve (-24.65, 28.67); Polokwane Nature Reserve (-23.9, 29.47); Potgietersrus/Mokopane (-24.17, 29.1); Sovenga Hill (-23.88, 29.73); Blouberg Nature Reserve (-23.12, 29.01); Gundani Forest (-22.655, 30.532). **Mpumalanga:** Brondal (-25.35, 30.84); Burgers Hall (-25.08, 31.06); Crocodile Valley Estate (-25.47, 31.03); Glenwood (-25.48, 30.92); Nelspruit (-25.47, 30.96); Schagen (-25.43, 30.8).

North West: Hartebeespoort (-25.6, 27.82). **Western Cape:** Bontebok National Park (-34.07, 20.45); De Hoop Nature Reserve (-34.45, 20.44); Uitzicht Annex (-34.0, 23.33); Kirstenbosch National Botanical Garden (-23.67, 28.38). Knysna, Uitzicht Annex (-34.00, 23.33).

LIFE STYLE

They are free-living plant dwellers and were sampled during SANSa surveys from the Fynbos, Grassland (Haddad *et al.*, 2013), Savanna (Foord *et al.*, 2011), and Thicket biomes (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2020). Sampling was mainly done by sweeping and beating methods.

During surveys in agroecosystems in the Mpumalanga province in South Africa, knock-sprays were used to sample spiders in avocado and macadamia orchards. In the avocado orchards, *O. argenteooculata* was the most abundant species sampled, representing 22.2% of all spiders collected during the year-long survey (n=826) (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2005). The species were commonly observed on leaves of the avocado trees, where they blend in with their green flattened bodies. *Oxytate* specimens are not commonly found and this was the first time that an *Oxytate* species has been collected in such high numbers from orchards in Africa. The adults were sampled throughout the year, and juveniles were sampled from May until October.

The surveys in macadamia orchards were undertaken during the same period in the same area but yielded only 12 specimens from three orchards (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2001). Further surveys in agroecosystems showed that the species has also been sampled from citrus orchards and from tomato fields (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2013) as well as from cotton fields (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 1999) but in lower numbers. They have been observed to feed on a variety of insects (Fig. 22) and mites.

The second author photographed a female with her egg sac in Heidelberg, Gauteng. The white, round sac was deposited on the ventral side a leaf. The egg sac was then covered with several thin layers of silk covering a large area of the leaf (Figs 15–16). The female took up position on the egg sac (Fig. 16), where she stayed to guard it until the eggs hatched (Fig. 17). In the same area a juvenile spider was photographed preparing to balloon (Figs 18–20).

CONSERVATION MEASURES

The species has a wide distribution in the Afrotropical Region and in South Africa it was sampled from eight of the nine provinces. Due to its wide geographical range, the species is therefore listed as Least Concern.

There are no known threats to the species and in South Africa it is recorded from several protected areas. The following survey results were published: Addo Elephant National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2020); Thyspunt (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Wiese, 2022); Ndumo Game Reserve (Haddad *et al.*, 2006); Luvhondo Nature Reserve (Foord *et al.*, 2008); Nylsvley Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2009); Polokwane Nature Reserve (Dippenaar *et al.*, 2008); Bontebok National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 201) and De Hoop Nature Reserve (Haddad & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2009).

Figs 12–23. *Oxytate argenteooculata*: 12. Male from Kloof. 13. Immature male from Kloof. 14. Female from Irene. 15–17. Female with egg sac and spiderlings from Heidelberg. 18–19. Spider from Heidelberg in process to start ballooning. 21. Spider as found on leaves. 22. Female busy feeding. 23. Female eye pattern. Photos: 12. Bruce Blake. 13 & 23. Andrea Sander. 14. Peter Webb. 15–22. Johan van Zyl.

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